

EXPLORATION OF THE DISCIPLINARY CONSTRUCTION PATH FOR LOCAL NEWLY-ESTABLISHED UNDERGRADUATE NORMAL UNIVERSITIES — A CASE STUDY OF THE SCHOOL OF MATHEMATICS AND STATISTICS, JINING NORMAL UNIVERSITY

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Abstract

Local newly-established undergraduate normal universities are an important pillar in the popularization of higher education in China, undertaking the core mission of cultivating high-quality teachers for regional basic education and serving local economic and social development. As a key normal university in the central and western regions of Inner Mongolia Autonomous Region, the disciplinary construction of the School of Mathematics and Statistics of Jining Normal University is directly related to the improvement of mathematics education quality and the supply of data application talents in Ulanqab City and surrounding areas. From the perspective of applied talent training and combined with the actual school-running situation of Jining Normal University, this paper analyzes the background and significance of disciplinary construction in local newly-established undergraduate normal universities, examines the prominent problems existing in current disciplinary construction, and puts forward targeted optimization strategies, so as to provide practical reference for the high-quality disciplinary development of similar universities.

Keywords: Local newly-established undergraduate normal universities; Disciplinary construction; Applied talents; Jining Normal University.

1 Background and Significance of Disciplinary Construction

1.1 Research Background

As China's higher education enters the stage of connotative development, the Inner Mongolia Autonomous Region has clearly put forward the strategic requirement of "strengthening the characteristic development of normal universities and improving the quality of basic education teacher training". As the only undergraduate normal university in Ulanqab City, Jining Normal University has always focused on the school-running orientation of "a distinctive and high-level local applied normal university in the western region" since it was upgraded to an undergraduate university. As one of the core colleges of the university, the School of Mathematics and Statistics has its disciplinary foundation rooted in the former mathematics education major at the junior college level. In the process of upgrading and transformation, it not only faces the common challenges of transforming from junior college education to undergraduate education, but also undertakes the dual tasks of adapting to the "quality improvement of basic education" and the "growing demand for regional data application" in the central and western regions of Inner Mongolia. At present, the mathematics education in primary and secondary schools in Ulanqab City has problems such as shortage of high-quality teachers and backward teaching methods. At the same time, local industries have an increasingly urgent demand for information and computing science talents in fields such as data analysis, big data, and artificial intelligence, which provides a clear direction for the disciplinary construction of the School of Mathematics and Statistics.

1.2 Significance of the Research

(1) Consolidate the foundation of educational quality. Disciplinary construction is a core means for the School of Mathematics and Statistics to improve teaching quality. By optimizing the curriculum system and integrating cutting-edge teaching concepts, it can

promote students majoring in mathematics education to master modern teaching methods and digital teaching skills, thereby supplying high-quality mathematics teachers who are proficient in teaching and good at innovation to local primary and secondary schools.

(2) Strengthen the development of the teaching staff. A high-quality disciplinary platform can attract high-education and senior-title talents to settle in the border areas. Meanwhile, it provides a practical carrier for existing teachers to conduct academic research and teaching reform, forming a positive cycle featuring simultaneous introduction and cultivation of talents and mutual promotion of teaching and research, so as to build a high-quality teaching team that meets the needs of the region.

(3) Precisely serve local development. Disciplinary construction can realize the empowerment of mathematics education serving basic education and aligning with regional demands. On one hand, it addresses the prominent problems of insufficient quantity and low quality of mathematics teachers in local primary and secondary schools; on the other hand, it provides technical support and talent guarantees for data processing fields such as data analysis, big data and artificial intelligence in local industries of Ulanqab City.

(4) In the competitive landscape of normal universities in the autonomous region, the distinctive School of Mathematics and Statistics can become a competitive calling card of Jining Normal University. It helps the university attract high-quality students, secure research projects and policy support, and enhance its discourse power in the regional higher education system.

2 Problems Existing in Disciplinary Construction

2.1 Insufficient Adaptability Between Disciplinary Orientation and Regional Demands

There is a tendency of "generalized imitation" in the direction of disciplinary development, failing to fully combine the educational needs and industrial

characteristics of Ulanqab City and surrounding areas. For example, the mathematics education direction still focuses on the imparting of traditional disciplinary knowledge, without highlighting the particularity of mathematics teaching in Inner Mongolia; information and computing science lacks in-depth integration with local industrial fields such as data analysis, big data, and artificial intelligence, resulting in an indistinct disciplinary feature.

2.2 Single Disciplinary Structure and Insufficient Interdisciplinary Integration

The disciplinary layout is concentrated in traditional fields such as mathematics education and pure mathematics, with the lagging development of emerging interdisciplinary directions. The lack of distinctive interdisciplinary disciplines leads to an insignificant disciplinary cluster effect, making it difficult to meet the needs of modern educational diversification and regional development for compound talents.

2.3 Structural Shortcomings in the Construction of the Teaching Staff

Restricted by factors such as geographical location and treatment conditions, it is difficult to introduce and cultivate talents with high academic qualifications and senior professional titles. Among the existing teaching staff, the proportion of teachers with doctoral degrees is relatively low, and there are few teachers with interdisciplinary backgrounds and first-line teaching and practical experience. The teacher training and development mechanism is not perfect, and the scientific research ability and practical teaching level need to be improved.

2.4 Weak Synergy between Scientific Research and Practice

The construction of scientific research platforms lags behind, and there is a lack of characteristic research carriers that meet regional needs. As a result, most scientific research projects focus on theoretical research and are not closely combined with the reality of local basic education reform and industrial development. The scientific research incentive mechanism is not sound enough, teachers' enthusiasm for participating in applied research is not high, and the transformation rate of scientific research achievements is low.

2.5 Insufficient Guarantee and Integration Ability of Disciplinary Resources

In terms of hardware facilities, the renewal of practical training facilities such as the mathematical modeling laboratory is not timely, and the reserve of resources including books and materials as well as professional databases is difficult to meet the needs of disciplinary development. In terms of resource integration, the cross-departmental resource sharing mechanism within the university has not yet been established, and the cooperation with local education bureaus, primary and secondary schools, and enterprises is not in-depth enough, failing to form a sound ecological environment featuring "university-local coordination and resource complementarity".

2.6 Disconnection between Practical Teaching and Job Requirements

The practical teaching link still mainly focuses on educational internships, and the internship content is

mostly classroom teaching observation and simple teaching, lacking systematic training in teaching skills and data analysis ability for normal students. The construction of practical bases is insufficient in quantity and low in quality, and it is difficult to provide practical scenarios that match job requirements, resulting in a gap between students' practical ability and the expectations of local employers.

3 Strategies for Disciplinary Construction of Local Newly-established Undergraduate Normal Universities

3.1 Anchor Regional Demands and Clarify Distinctive Disciplinary Orientation

Conduct in-depth research on the current status of mathematics education in primary and secondary schools in Ulanqab City and the demand for data talents from regional industrial development, and formulate a "two-wheel-driven" disciplinary development plan. On one hand, focus on the quality improvement of basic education, create distinctive directions, and prioritize cultivating teachers familiar with local primary and secondary school mathematics teaching. On the other hand, align with regional development needs, build characteristic tracks, and train applied talents for local industrial fields such as data analysis, big data, and artificial intelligence. Meanwhile, integrate the disciplinary orientation into the higher education development plan of the autonomous region and the education development outline of Ulanqab City to secure policy and resource support.

3.2 Optimize the Disciplinary Structure and Promote Interdisciplinary Integration and Development

(1) Consolidate the advantages of traditional disciplines, deepen the connotative development of core disciplines such as mathematics education and pure mathematics, update the curriculum system, and integrate cutting-edge content such as digital teaching and core literacy cultivation.

(2) Expand emerging interdisciplinary disciplines, add interdisciplinary directions including "Data Science and Educational Big Data Analysis" and "Artificial Intelligence", and form a disciplinary layout featuring "traditional disciplines laying the foundation and interdisciplinary disciplines empowering development".

(3) Establish a disciplinary coordination mechanism, break down inter-college barriers, carry out interdisciplinary cooperation with the School of Computer Science, School of Liberal Arts, School of Life Sciences, etc., and jointly offer courses such as "Mathematical Modeling and Programming" and "Research on Mathematical Culture" to cultivate compound talents.

3.3 Strengthen Faculty Development and Build a High-Quality Teaching Team

(1) Optimize talent introduction policies, and jointly launch a "Special Program for Borderland Education Talents" with local governments. Provide preferential treatments such as relocation allowances, research start-up funds, and children's education support for introduced doctors and professors; focus on recruiting compound talents with primary and secondary

school mathematics teaching experience and regional data processing practice experience.

(2) Improve the teacher training mechanism and establish a trinity training model of "on-campus training + off-campus visiting studies + enterprise practice". Encourage teachers to pursue doctoral degrees and establish a joint training mechanism with universities such as Inner Mongolia University and Inner Mongolia Normal University; regularly organize teachers to participate in activities such as national mathematics education seminars; arrange teachers to take temporary positions in local primary and secondary schools and participate in practical projects in enterprises to improve their practical capabilities.

(3) Improve the incentive mechanism, incorporate interdisciplinary teaching, applied research achievements, and local service performance into the core indicators for professional title evaluation and post promotion, so as to stimulate teachers' enthusiasm for teaching, research and serving the local community.

3.4 Build Characteristic Platforms and Enhance the Synergy between Scientific Research and Practice

(1) Construct characteristic scientific research platforms, and jointly establish a "Regional Mathematics Education Research Center" with the Ulanqab Municipal Bureau of Education. Focus on conducting research on topics such as local mathematics teaching reform, data analysis, big data, and artificial intelligence to provide practical carriers for disciplinary development.

(2) Deepen university-local cooperation, co-construct "Mathematics Education Practice Bases" with key primary and secondary schools in Ulanqab City, and carry out cooperation such as joint teaching and research and teaching reform pilots; co-establish "Data Application Practice Bases" with local departments such as the Big Data Bureau to provide students with real project practice opportunities.

(3) Strengthen the orientation of scientific research output, encourage teachers to apply for regional projects such as educational science planning projects of Inner Mongolia Autonomous Region and science and technology plan projects of Ulanqab City, and carry out research focusing on local practical issues; establish a scientific research achievement transformation mechanism, transform research achievements into teaching cases, local development consulting reports, etc., so as to enhance the social influence of the discipline.

3.5 Integrate Internal and External Resources to Strengthen Disciplinary Guarantee Capabilities

(1) Optimize the allocation of internal school resources, secure special fund support from the university, and update practical training facilities such as the mathematical modeling laboratory; establish an internal shared resource library, integrate resources including books and materials, professional databases, and experimental equipment to improve the efficiency of resource utilization.

(2) Expand external resource channels, take the initiative to connect with the Department of Education of Inner Mongolia Autonomous Region and the Ulanqab

Municipal Government to obtain policy inclination and fund investment; establish cooperative relations with high-level normal universities and scientific research institutes inside and outside the region to share high-quality teaching resources and scientific research platforms; attract enterprise donations and social sponsorships to broaden funding sources.

3.6 Deepen Practical Teaching Reform and Improve the Quality of Talent Training

(1) Construct a "three-stage progressive" practical teaching system. In the basic stage, strengthen the training of teaching skills and data processing capabilities; in the core stage, carry out immersive practice through internship bases; in the improvement stage, organize students to participate in practical training such as mathematical modeling competitions and local data processing projects.

(2) Innovate practical teaching content, compile practical textbooks integrating mathematical culture and regional data cases; add practical courses such as artificial intelligence to enhance students' ability to adapt to local positions.

(3) Improve the practical evaluation mechanism, adopt a trinity evaluation model of "school evaluation + base evaluation + industry evaluation", and incorporate practical performance and project achievements into the students' comprehensive evaluation system to ensure the quality of practical teaching.

4 Implementation Guarantees

(1) Organizational Guarantee: Establish a leading group for disciplinary construction, led by the dean of the college. It will include experts from inside and outside the university, responsible persons of local educational administrative departments, and backbone teachers from primary and secondary schools to coordinate the implementation of the disciplinary construction plan and process management.

(2) System Guarantee: Formulate a series of system documents such as the "Measures for the Administration of Disciplinary Construction", the "Implementation Plan for the Construction of the Teaching Staff", and the "Measures for Rewards for Scientific Research and Social Services" to standardize all links of disciplinary construction and ensure the effective implementation of strategies.

(3) Financial Guarantee: Establish a diversified financial guarantee mechanism of "university investment + local support + social fundraising", incorporate disciplinary construction funds into the college's annual budget, and give priority to guaranteeing investment in core areas such as talent introduction, platform construction, and practical teaching.

5 Conclusion

The disciplinary construction of local newly-established undergraduate normal universities is a long-term and systematic project. It needs to be based on their own realities, closely linked to regional needs, and take a distinctive and application-oriented development path. For the disciplinary construction of the School of Mathematics and Statistics of Jining Normal University, it is necessary not only to solve the common problems in the transformation and development but also to give full play to the regional characteristics and normal

school advantages. Through measures such as clarifying the distinctive orientation, optimizing the disciplinary structure, strengthening the faculty construction, and deepening university-local cooperation, the level of disciplinary construction will be continuously improved. In the future, the college will continue to focus on the core goal of cultivating applied talents, take disciplinary construction as the leading role, promote the coordinated development of teaching, scientific research, and social services, and provide more powerful talent support and intellectual guarantee for the quality improvement of basic education and economic and social development in Ulanqab City and the central and western regions of Inner Mongolia.

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